

SATELLITE PROPULSION COMPOSITE TANKS FOR SPACE SHUTTLE APPLICATIONS

Pramod SHANKAR *

*TRW - Post Office Box 1310
San Bernardino, California 92402*

In satellite propulsion subsystems, several types of tanks may be used for storing fuels, oxidizers, and pressurants. In order to define and optimize composite tank designs for shuttle-optimized spacecraft propulsion subsystems in the early 1980's various tank configurations must be studied. For longer mission life requirements (typically 10 years) and limited payload volume, it is important to look at more efficient weights and packaging schemes, and material compatibility problems. The optimization of this study is centered around the themes, that launch cost reductions can be achieved for spacecraft which minimize length requirements in the shuttle cargo bay, and delivery schedule reductions appear probable if the use of titanium tanks is avoided. Various tank/structure configurations have been investigated in this effort.

This paper is a brief summary of this effort and describes the collected information for composite propulsion tanks as applicable to space shuttle optimized spacecraft designs. Topics of analysis and design, materials, weight trade-offs, propellant management devices, safety issues, and testing have been addressed. Some general conclusions are drawn and recommendations are made for utilizing advanced composite propulsion tanks in the near future.

* Formerly at Ford Aerospace & Electronics Company-Western Development Laboratories, Palo Alto, California, whose support for this project through their Space Division IR & D program is acknowledged.

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

In communications satellite propulsion subsystems, several types of tanks may be used for fuels, oxidizers, and pressurants. In order to define and optimize designs for shuttle-optimized spacecraft propulsion subsystems in the early 1980's, various tank configurations must be studied. For longer mission life requirements (typically 10 years) and limited payload volume, it is important to look at more efficient weights and packaging schemes.

The emphasis of this study is centered around the following two themes,

- a. Significant launch cost reductions can be achieved for spacecraft which minimize length requirements in the shuttle cargo bay.
- b. Significant delivery schedule reductions appear probable if the use of titanium tanks is avoided.

Alternate tank/structure configurations have been investigated in this effort, including (1) simple spherical, elliptical and cylindrical tanks (each tank and primary structure are independent), (2) compound or nested tanks (adjacent tanks share a common bulkhead, but the tanks and primary structure are independent), (3) integrated tanks (tank and primary structures are integrated and interdependent).

The factors of consideration are weight trade-offs, materials selection information, analyses, design procedures, fabrication procedures, propellant management devices, safety, testing, costs, and delivery schedules.

This paper is a brief summary of this effort and describes the collected information for propulsion tanks as applicable to spacecraft applications. Subsequent sections address the topics of analysis and design, materials, weight trade-offs, propellant management devices, safety issues, and testing. Some general conclusions are drawn and recommendations are made for utilizing advanced composite propulsion tanks in the near future.

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Proven mechanical engineering practice (e.g. ASME codes) provide the foundation for the design of homogeneous metallic pressure vessels. The first military specification for all composite tanks (MIL-T-25363) was written for aerospace usage. The all-composite cylindrical tanks were generally constructed by filament-winding over a disposable mandrel which was covered with an elastomeric sealant liner connected to metal bosses. This resulted in a pressure vessel in which the filament-wound composite wall provided all the required strength, and the elastomeric sealant liner provided an impermeable membrane which contained the pressurizing medium. Tanks of this description provide substantial mass economies and are used for special aerospace and commercial applications.

Currently, the all-composite tank has disadvantages as far as some spacecraft service is concerned. The existence of an applied stress field within the walls of a composite pressure vessel will usually result in the formation of resin matrix crazes and cracks. These defects are often sufficient to permit the loss of the pressurizing medium. To avoid this, a sealant liner is required. However, an elastomeric sealant liner is not resistant to deterioration under many practical service conditions. The major areas of concern are (1) high pressures (where permeation may introduce problems), (2) low temperatures (where elastomers become brittle and have insufficient extensibility), and/or (3) compatibility with the pressurizing medium. For these situations, metallic sealant liners must be used.

During the 1960's, the use of thin metallic sealant liners grew. These thin liners were adhesively bonded to the composite filament-wound overwrap to produce the lightest weight heterogeneous vessels. The purpose of the adhesive bond was

to transfer longitudinal and circumferential hoop loads from the thin metal shell to the composite overwrap by shear. Research demonstrated the capability of the adhesive bond and cyclic life capabilities for several combinations of overwrap and liner materials. The cyclic life of such vessels has been shown to be severely limited by the high plastic strain cycle induced in the metal liner during pressure cycling and by the adhesive bond strength integrity required. The structural capacity of any bond depends upon the magnitude of the maximum shear stress developed within the adhesive, rather than on the average shearing stresses along the joint. In all shear joints, high concentrations of stresses occur at the ends (terminal areas of overwrap), where the greatest portion of load is transferred. During service, if this stress concentration is greater than the allowable shear stress of the adhesive, the bond is destroyed through adhesive failure. In view of the potentially unreliable features of an adhesive bond between the thin metal liner and composite overwrap, it is a conservative practice to ignore any beneficial effect that may be produced by a bond. Circumferential loads may still be transferred from the metal shell to the composite overwrap without the existence of an adhesive bond through the simple bearing of one shell upon the other. This concept is used when the cylindrical sections of homogeneous metal tanks are reinforced in order to reduce the circumferential operational stresses. For many practical designs involving the use of thin metal sealant liners, this approach is often the most efficient and suitable. In order to simplify trade-off studies to arrive at the effect of judiciously overwrapping a thin metallic liner with continuous composite filaments, the following assumptions may be used,

- a. A membrane state of stress exists. Discontinuities in shell curvature, thickness, and materials are ignored.
- b. No bond exists between the metallic shell liner and the overwrap material. This assumption implies that the composite overwrap is not subjected to loads in the transverse direction (i.e. no Poisson effect).
- c. Composite filaments are applied under zero tension. This feature requires the absence of prestresses in the composite overwrap (tensile) and the thin metallic liner (compressive).
- d. Potential thermoelastic strains induced during fabrication are ignored.

During the course of aerospace pressure vessel technology growth, several innovative approaches have been used to produce tanks which possess thin-metal sealant liners. In striving for maximum efficiencies, all-composite filament wound tanks have been produced and then subjected to vacuum and/or electrodeposition processes to produce an impermeable membrane within the vessel. However, the choice of such an approach must be predicated on the basis of maximum operating pressures and permeability requirements. In the 1960's efforts led to improved design methods for filament overwrapped pressure vessel configurations which were leak-proof, suitable for cryogenic service, and which cleverly matched the dissimilar strengths and elastic moduli of the composite and sealant metal liner to yield ultra-lightweight tanks. By this time the aerospace industry was adopting the concepts of safe-life design, based on reliability considerations as opposed to simple safety factors, to meet the stringent light-weight requirements of the space age. Coupled with the emerging disciplines of composites technology and fracture mechanics, there was the extended development of prestressed composite/load bearing metal lined tanks using a wide variety of composite and metallic materials. The prestressing (or sizing) process is an efficient design tool for maximizing pressure vessel efficiencies.

During the 1970's, pressure vessel technology began to utilize thick metal sealant liners for purposes of producing the prestressed composite/load sharing metal liner system. Filament-wound tanks with load-sharing metal liners are usually intermediate in weight savings performance between thin-metal/bonded liner composite tanks and homo-generous metal tanks, and do not require an adhesive bond between the metal shell and the overwrap (i.e., load transfer mechanism is still bearing). These types of pressure vessels are usually most suitable for high pressure systems.

The primary objective in the design of a fiber reinforced metal pressure vessel is to obtain maximum operating performance at minimum mass, and to provide safe life design features. The design criteria fix the relative thickness of the metal sealant liner and overwrapped composite structure. In general, the metal liner thickness is 25% to 50% of the thickness a homogeneous metal vessel would need to be to carry the pressure loads. Tank weight reduction comes from the high strength and low weight of the overwrap. In decreasing order of strength efficiency, the following filament-wound composites have been evaluated: (1) Kevlar-49/Epoxy, (2) Graphite/Epoxy, (3) S-2, and E-glass/Epoxy and, (4) Boron/Epoxy. For stiffness considerations, this ranking may change.

ANALYSIS CONSIDERATIONS

Structural analysis efforts proceed in two different directions, depending upon whether the tank structure is all metallic or also consists of a composite overwrap. For all-metal tanks, preliminary membrane sizing can be done by simple pressure vessel analysis techniques. However, a complicated loads, frequency, and stress analyses must also be performed to verify the structural integrity under launch environments such as quasi-static accelerations, sine and acoustic vibrations, and shock loads. This can be accomplished by standard computer analysis techniques typically used for satellite primary structures.

For composite tanks with metal liners the design procedure is more complicated. One simple way of analyzing such tanks is to ignore the metal liner, and design the composite overwrap as a simple pressure vessel. Obviously, this imposes a certain mass penalty on the structure. The least mass design is obtained when the liner acts as a load-sharing member, and must be designed as such. At the curing temperature of the composite, both the composite wrap and the metal liner are essentially stress-free. When the tank is cooled down to room temperature, the liner goes into compression and the composite wrap goes into tension. Subsequent to curing, a "sizing" pressure is imposed which stretches the liner into the plastic range. For subsequent pressurizations, the liner then acts elastically in an expended loading region, going from compression to tension. Analysis of such a tank, therefore, must consider nonlinear plastic effects and buckling of the liner under compression. Optimizing for both buckling and maximum elasto-plastic range is a complicated procedure. Another analytical aspect of tank design is the evaluation of fracture mechanics effects. For metal tanks, the techniques are well developed with sufficient documentation and computer programs. Fracture mechanics of composite materials is still in the developing stages and several guidelines are available for design. Long term effects of stresses on composites is still a subject of research but initial results appear encouraging. The fracture of composite reinforced tanks shows a very desirable feature of leak-before-burst, thus reducing safety hazards.

MATERIALS

The materials of construction for homogeneous metal tanks are usually titanium, steel or aluminum. The use of high strength steel in the commercial sector is most common. In aerospace applications, titanium is most widely used. Some aluminum alloys are compatible with spacecraft fuels and oxidizers but their long term effects are still unknown. These same comments also apply to the metal liner in a composite tank. Three of the most common liner materials are 2219-T62 aluminum, cryoformed 301 stainless steel, and Inconel 750. However, the load sharing concept is usually the most weight efficient for high pressure tanks (above 1000 psi) and is usually a good candidate for pressurant tanks. When moderate pressures are used, use of reinforced load bearing thin metal sealant liners is often preferable. For lower pressure tank applications either electro-deposited (.005 to .010 in., depending upon permeability requirements) or bonded thin metal liners usually offer greater advantages. These statements are somewhat general and are meant to

serve as a simplified guide. A wide variety of composite and metallic materials have been used in aerospace tanks. Excellent results have been obtained from Kevlar-49 and S-Glass composites with steel, stainless steel, inconel, titanium, and aluminum alloy liners. The properties of the composite overwrap are highly dependent upon the filament characteristics. The more homogeneous continuum provided by smaller diameter glass filaments is often an important consideration as it provides higher reliability. The most common matrices are high grade heat-curing epoxies. The filaments can be impregnated with resin during the overwrap operations (i.e. winding), or purchased as pre-impregnated strands.

Epoxies with anhydride curing agents have seen wide usage. However, such epoxies are prone to high moisture absorption and suffer from low maximum elongations. The effect of epoxy resin modulus on the structural efficiency of a tank (defined as burst pressure X volume/weight) of Kevlar-49/epoxy vessels has been studied by NASA-Lewis who found that highly extensible (low modulus) epoxy resins provide a 30% increase in tank efficiency over vessels of identical designs but made with conventional epoxies.

It is appropriate to review the structural indices of specified strengths and specific moduli of filament overwrap candidates. It should be noted, however, that for the load-sharing concept, it is often difficult to justify the use of low modulus filaments. A low filament modulus of elasticity often negates the effectiveness of reducing metal wall stresses.

The effects of overwrap materials on tank weights are often complex because of the necessity to match the dissimilar material moduli and strengths. Figure 1 provides a comparative review of materials for spherical pressure vessels.

To develop and establish filament-reinforced load-sharing metal tank designs, filament safe operating stress levels are used in conjunction with the metal shell safe-operating stress level to develop a configuration which maximizes those allowable stresses at operating pressures and which also provide the required pressure vessel burst strength within minimum ultimate strength capabilities. This means letting the metal have maximum allowable compression at zero pressure (for load sharing) and maximum allowable operating stress at operating pressure and temperature. Actual design development consists of parametric studies of constituent material stresses at conditions of interest and the attendant mass changes for given operating and burst pressures.

Filament winding is a well-developed technology for simple composite pressure vessels, such as rocket motor cases or tanks. However, the winding of vessels that contain reversed curvatures or variable diameters requires more advanced fabrication technology. This difficulty can often be reduced by using honeycomb pressure vessel designs. The nested (common bulkhead) and integrated tank structure designs are probably best suited for honeycomb design approach. A combination design using localized composite overwrapping of sandwich walls can also be employed.

WEIGHT TRADE-OFFS

Optimum weight design of a propulsion subsystem must consider the weight of the propellants, pressurants, tanks, thrusters, miscellaneous connectors, regulators, valves, and the feed system. (The feed system can be a pressurant type or a pump feed type, and involves some power trade-offs). In this section attention will be focused on propellant tanks and geometry considerations with emphasis on bipropellant systems where a fuel and an oxidizer tank are considered jointly. Pressurant tanks and monopropellant system tanks are essentially single unit tanks, for which a spherical shape is always the optimum. (Any departure from the spherical to a cylindrical shape in view of geometrical constraints incurs mass penalty and will be discussed as part of the bipropellant system).

In most of the results presented, only the tank shell weights have been con-

sidered. Weights for support brackets, propellant management devices various bosses, etc. have been ignored. Hence, the results presented in this section should be modified for these factors for each particular design. For low design pressures, buckling strength under external atmospheric pressures may become the controlling design criterion.

The efficiency of gain in volume versus increase in weight as one departs from spherical to a cylindrical or elliptical configuration without increasing the overall length of the diameter shown in Figure 2 and 3.

Switching from the spherical tank design to a common bulkhead tank provides considerable economy in volumetric efficiency. Assuming the diameters and overall lengths are either kept constant or changed (to match volumes), one can easily see the impact on mass in Figure 4. The common bulkhead may be designed to withstand any desired pressure differential between the tank chambers.

Structural vs nonstructural tanks trade-off is difficult to perform in a general case, since the structural tank must be designed in detail as a satellite primary structure. Even though structural tank approach may be the most mass efficient, many difficulties exist. Problems of testing, assembly, safety, etc. become major issues and development effort may be required before this idea can be successfully used.

PROPELLANT MANAGEMENT

There are problems associated with propellant orientation and control in a zero-g or negative-g environment. Therefore, a method for maintaining propellant at the tank outlets is required so that gas-free liquids are available to rocket engines on demand. Propellant management devices provide this method of control. This section qualitatively compares current internal propellant management methods for possible application to spacecraft. The tank configuration of main interest is of a nested or common bulkhead geometry. The liquids to be stored and managed for 7 to 10 years are restricted to N_2O_4 (nitrogen tetroxide) and MMH (monomethylhydrazine).

Dielectrophoretic Systems approach is attractive only when propellants with low electrical conductivity are used. Monomethylhydrazine has high electrical conductivity which makes the power requirement of a dielectrophoretic system excessive. Polymeric Bladders and Diaphragms materials are permeable to pressurant gas and propellant vapor and limited in chemical and thermal compatibility. These devices have usually been limited to systems with storage requirements of less than a year. Metal Telephragms, Bonded Rolling Diaphragms, and Transverse Collapsing Bladders are types of design which can tolerate little, or no, flexing of the diaphragm or bladder due to thermal expansion, slosh, and vibration, or metal fatigue will result.

It is recommended that these concepts not be considered as potential design candidates for a nested or common bulkhead tank geometry. The metal convoluted spherical diaphragms are only applicable to spherical tanks. The metal ring-reinforced diaphragms are an attractive design concept. The capillary/bellows concept will easily interface with a common bulkhead tank, however, it relies upon engine thrust for settling the propellant at the tank outlet. This directed settling acceleration is not always available in orbit for spacecrafts.

Propellant management systems which appear most attractive for applications to common bulkhead tank geometries are metal bellows and surface tension devices. The bellows are closed containers with convoluted side walls that fit within the tank container. Metal bellows systems are inherently heavy. A number of capillary or surface tension systems have been developed and several have performed satisfactorily in flight. These systems appear to be easily adaptable to a common

bulkhead tank geometry. Tests necessary to demonstrate the operational readiness of a propellant management subsystem are Structural Integrity Tests and Expulsion Efficiency Tests.

The management system is considered part of the tank structure and must pass subsystem structural vibration testing. The types of expulsion efficiency tests performed depend upon the management subsystem design and propellant orientation requirements. Expulsion efficiency of surface tension devices are verified from drop tower and bench tests.

In summary, a large number of options is available for propellant management devices for spherical tanks. Of these options, only metal bellows and surface tension type devices can be used for cylindrical nested tanks with common bulkheads. The metal bellows devices are usually heavier than the surface tension devices. These devices are tested for structural integrity as part of subsystem mechanical testing, and for expulsion efficiency using drop tower and bench tests.

SAFETY REQUIREMENTS AND TESTING

For shuttle payloads, NASA imposes many safety requirements to eliminate or control safety hazards caused by unsafe acts or conditions. For propulsion subsystem tanks, these hazards consist of leakage or release of toxic, flammable, corrosive, condensible, or particulate matter. Leakage of hazardous fluids can be initiated from cracks or worn seals, gaskets, valve seats, flanges and joints. Corrosion, resulting in structural degradation of metallic and nonmetallic equipment is considered hazardous. Corrosion may also result from material incompatibility or the joining of certain dissimilar metals. Stress corrosion, electrolytic corrosion, and polymerization processes must also be considered. The overpressurization of tanks may lead to violent release of energy (explosion) and post a hazard. Special attention must be given to the design and test of pressure vessels and related contour devices to prevent the possibility of explosion. For example, pressure vessels should meet the requirements of NSS/MP-1740 "Aerospace Pressure Vessel Fracture Control". Fracture mechanics analysis must be performed to determine flaw growth, stress corrosion, failure modes, and other related material characteristics. Each pressure vessel must pass qualification tests to demonstrate compliance with design requirements. Each vessel must also pass acceptance tests to prove its flight acceptability.

A detailed list of guidelines may be found in the section 2.11 of ref. (26). Section 2.12 of the same reference lists the flammability and toxic properties of propellants. It clearly states that common bulkheads between fuel and oxidizer tanks of hypergolic propellants should be avoided. Also hypergolic fuels and oxidizers should not be separated by a single weld.

CONCLUSIONS

This section lists some general conclusions. However, a detailed analysis is recommended in each situation to validate these conclusions and arrive at an optimum decision.

- (I) Pressurant tanks are usually high pressure gas tanks operating at pressures of several thousand psi. For such tanks a spherical shape is the optimum and a filament wound composite with load sharing metal liner construction offers the best mass and schedule advantages. The pressurant usually is an inert gas which does not react with the steel liner. Aluminum liners may also be considered. In view of the geometrical constraints, a cylindrical tank may also be used with some mass penalty. Several sources exist with capability for analysis, design, fabrication, and testing of such tanks. Average lead times can be expected to be approximately three to six months.

- (II) Fuel and oxidizer tanks usually operate at low pressures of the order of 300 psi. For such tanks two aspects are important. First is the chemical compatibility of the liner material with the fuel and oxidizer over a life up to 10 years and the other is the best mix of mass and procurement schedule efficiency. Titanium tanks have the lowest mass but have the disadvantage of very long lead times in procurement. It appears that the best alternatives for mass and schedule is filament wound aluminum liner tanks.
- (III) Almost all propellant management devices are applicable for spherical tanks. For cylindrical compound tanks it appears that surface tension type devices are best suited.
- (IV) Safety aspects are usually taken care of by the use of proper design criteria for burst strength and fracture failure. For a nested tank storing fuel and oxidizer, the common bulkhead must be a dual wall construction to meet NASA safety requirements. Fiber reinforced composite wall construction tanks are preferred since they possess a leak-before-burst feature which minimizes the risk of catastrophic failure.
- (V) Conventional linear-elastic fracture mechanics for establishing critical failure conditions at the operating stresses can be used as operating stresses are always within the elastic limit. An acceptable fracture mechanics analysis is not available for post-yield stresses (required for load sharing, metal lined composite tanks). One must determine empirically the stress versus flaw size relationship in this region. These data establish the maximum initial flaw size.
- (VI) Several commercial test facilities are available to perform pressurization and pressure cycle testing of tanks. Propellant management are usually tested by building a model and facilities exist at several large aerospace companies to perform such testing.
- (VII) Extensive fabrication capability exists in the industry for metal liners, and composite overwrapping.
- (VIII) Structural tanks carry the primary loads and represent the most mass efficient designs but require detailed evaluation with respect to safety, assembly, and testing issues. Development effort is required before such systems can be proposed for application.
- (IX) Among spherical, cylindrical, elliptical, and nested tanks the spherical tanks represent the least mass option for a given volume of monopropellant or pressurant. However, for a bipropellant system, two stacked spheres are a very inefficient volume packaging configuration. For such cases it is essential to consider a cylindrical common bulkhead and elliptical tanks to minimize the length requirements in the shuttle bay. Such an approach shows better volume packaging but has associated mass penalty compared to the two spheres configuration.
- (X) Bulkheads of a common bulkhead tank may be designed for any pressure differential across the bulkhead if this differential is regulated. For unregulated pressure differentials, using the full burst pressure for design may result in conservative (heavy) designs. Two-thirds the burst pressure has been used in satellite applications, and also shows the surprising feature that the total tank membrane mass is independent of the diameter for a fixed volume.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. W. D. Bixler, "Fracture Control Method for Composite Tanks with Load Sharing Liners", NASA CR-134758 Boeing Aerospace Company, July 1975.
2. R. E. Landes, "Glass Fiber Reinforced Metal Pressure Vessel Design Guide", NASA CR-120917, Structural Composites Industries, July 1972.
3. J. N. Masters, W. D. Bixler and R. W. Finger, "Fracture Characteristics of Structural Aerospace Alloys Containing Deep Surface Flaws", NASA CR-134587, Boeing Aerospace Company, December 1973.
4. J. J. Kibler and R. Roberts, "The Effect of Biaxial Stresses on Fatigue and Fracture", Trans. of the ASME, Journal of Engineering for Industry, November 1970.
5. P. D. Hilton, "Plastic Intensity Factors for Cracked Plates Subject to Biaxial Loading", International Journal of Fracture, Vol. 9, No. 2, June 1973.
6. C. F. Tiffany, P. M. Lorenz and L. R. Hall, "Investigation of Plane-Strain Flaw Growth in Thick-Walled Tanks", NASA CR-54837, The Boeing Company, February 1966.
7. C. M. Hudson and J. T. Scardina, "Effect of Stress Ratio on Fatigue-Crack Growth in 7075-T6 Aluminum-Alloy Sheet", Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Col. 1, No. 3, April 1979.
8. W. Illg and A. J. McEvily Jr., "The Rate of Fatigue-Crack Propagation for Two Aluminum Alloys Under Completely Reversed Loading", NASA Technical Note D-52, Langley Research Center, October 1959.
9. D. R. Donaldson and W. E. Andersen, "Crack Propagation Behavior of Some Airframe Materials", Crack Propagation Symposium Proceedings-Cranfield, England, Vol. 2, September 1961.
10. T. W. Crooker, "Effect of Tension - Compression Cycling on Fatigue Crack Growth in High-Strength Alloys", NRL Report 7220, Naval Research Laboratory, January 1971.
11. J. N. Masters, W. P. Haese and R. W. Finger, "Investigation of Deep Flaws in Thin Walled Tanks", NASA CR-72606, The Boeing Company, December 1969.
12. J. N. Masters, W. L. Engstrom and W. D. Bixler, "Deep Flaws in Weldments of Aluminum and Titanium", NASA CR-134649, Boeing Aerospace Company, April 1974.
13. R. M. Bonesteel, "Fracture of Thin Sections Containing Surface Cracks", Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Vol. 5, No. 3, September 1973.
14. L. R. Hall and W. D. Bixler, "Subcritical Crank Growth of Selected Aerospace Pressure Vessel Materials", NASA CR-120834, The Boeing Company, December 1972.
15. L. R. Hall, R. C. Shah and W. L. Engstrom, "Fracture and Fatigue Crack Growth Behavior of Surface Flaws and Flaws Originating at Fastener Holes", AFFDL-TR-74-47, Boeing Aerospace Company, May 1974.

16. Darms, F. J. and Landes, R. E. "Computer Program for the Analysis of Filament-Reinforced Metal-Shell Pressure Vessels", NASA CR-72124, Aerojet-General Corporation, Rev. May 1972.
17. Morris, E.E., Darms, F. J., Landes, R. E., and Campbell, J. W. "Parametric Study of Glass-Filament-Reinforced Metal Pressure Vessels", NASA CR 54-855, Aerojet-General Corporation, April 1966.
18. Morris, E.E., "Glass-Fiber-Reinforced Metallic Tanks for Cryogenic Service" NASA CR-72224, Aerojet-General Corporation, June 1967.
19. Tiffany, C.F., "Fracture Control of Metallic Pressure Vessels", NASA Design Monograph SP-8040.
20. Buckling of Thin-Walled Doubly Curved Shells, NASA Space Vehicle Design Criteria, NASA SP-8032, August 1969.
21. Gleich, D., "Development of a Filament-Overwrapped Cyroformed Metal Pressure Vessel", NASA CR-72753, January 1971, Arde, Inc.
22. W. P. Patterson, R. Gordon, E. E. Morris, "Light-Weight, High Pressure Composite Pressure Vessels for Commercial Applications", 32nd Annual Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, The Society of the Plastic Industry, Inc., 1977.
23. R. E. Landes, E. E. Morris, "Composite Tanks for Aerospace Vehicle Application", 32nd Annual Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, The Society of the Plastics Industry, Inc. 1977.
24. R. E. Landes, "Filament Reinforcing Cylindrical Sections of LEM Descent Propulsion Tanks to Reduce Operating Stress Levels", Aerojet General, Electronics Division, Report No. 3709, February 1969.
25. R. E. Landes, "Filament-Reinforced Metal Composite Pressure Vessel Evaluation and Performance Demonstration", Final Report, NASA CR-134975, May 1976.
26. Space Transportation System Payload Safety Guidelines Handbook, NASA JSC 11123, July 1976.
27. M. E. Hamstad, "Aging Data for Kevlar 49/Epoxy Pressure Vessels", Composites Technology Review, Vol. 1, No. 3, 1979.
28. C. J. Elia, "Titanium Shortage May Slow Aircraft Market During Next Two Years as Plane Orders Boom", Wall Street Journal, Aug. 22, 1979.
29. T. T. Chiao, C. C. Chiao, and R. J. Sherry, "Lifetime of Fiber Composites Under Sustained Tensile Loading", Proc. Int. Conf. Fracture Mechanics and Technology, Eds. G. C. Sih and C. L. Chow, Noordhoof, 1977, pp. 257-270.

FIGURE 1. SPHERICAL PRESSURE VESSEL EFFICIENCIES

FIGURE 2. SPHERICAL VS DOMED CYLINDRICAL TANK

FIGURE 3. SPHERICAL VS COMMON BULKHEAD TANK

FIGURE 4. ELLIPTIC VS. SPHERICAL TANKS - VOLUME, WEIGHT, DIA., AND HEIGHT